

Antelope: Towards on-board anomaly detection in telemetry data using deep learning

Jakub Nalepa, Michal Myller, Pawel Benecki, Jacek Andrzejewski, and Daniel Kostrzewa

jnalepa@kplabs.pl

www.kplabs.pl

Smart Mission **Ecosystem** by KP LABS

HARDWARE, SOFTWARE AND AI-POWERED ALGORITHMS DESIGNED TO COMPLETE YOUR MISSION

3

ANTELOPE

On-board computer with predictive maintenance

ORYX

Modular on-board software

LEOPARD

High-performance data processing unit for AI applications

THE HERD

AI-powered algorithms for Earth Observation

OASIS

Electrical Ground Support Equipment created to test satellite on the Earth

Smart Mission **Ecosystem** by KP LABS

HARDWARE, SOFTWARE AND AI-POWERED ALGORITHMS DESIGNED TO COMPLETE YOUR MISSION

4

Barbara Pilastre, Loïc Boussof, Stéphane D'Escrivan, Jean-Yves Tournet; Anomaly detection in mixed telemetry data using a sparse representation and dictionary learning; Signal Processing, Volume 168, 2020

Anomaly detection in FDIR

- Failure Detection Isolation and Recovery: on-board systems dedicated for discovery of anomalies and entering safe state
- Current state of the art
 - **Out-of-limit checks**
 - **Machine learning algorithms, expert systems**
 - **Detailed analysis on the ground**

Anomaly detection in FDIR

- Failure Detection Isolation and Recovery: on-board systems dedicated for discovery of anomalies and entering safe state
- Current state of the art
 - **Out-of-limit checks** (How about periodic signals? Inter-parameter relations?)
 - **Machine learning algorithms, expert systems** (Training data? Parameterization? On-board implementation, e.g., FPGA?)
 - **Detailed analysis on the ground**
 - Need access to communication window
 - Human analysis and reaction necessary
 - Problem for small satellites with small teams and non-continuous communication
 - Data transfer (cost & time; which part of data is „relevant“?)

Towards on-board anomaly – why?

- Traditional out-of-limit FDIR systems often **detect point anomalies only**
- **Entering safe mode earlier** after failure undetectable by basic out-of-limits methods
- **Smaller amount of telemetric data** sent to Earth – more bandwidth available to other data

Towards on-board anomaly – why?

- Traditional out-of-limit FDIR systems often **detect point anomalies only**
- **Entering safe mode earlier** after failure undetectable by basic out-of-limits methods
- **Smaller amount of telemetric data** sent to Earth – more bandwidth available to other data
- Can we **predict** that something bad is about to happen?

Machine (deep) learning in anomaly detection

Deep recurrent neural network-based detector

Machine (deep) learning in anomaly detection

How to gather training data?

Telemetry „ground-truth” datasets

Telemanom (Detecting Spacecraft Anomalies Using LSTMs and Nonparametric Dynamic Thresholding; Hundman, Constantinou, Laporte, Colwell, Soderstrom; 2018 (NASA Jet Propulsion Laboratory) <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1802.04431.pdf>)

Telemetry „ground-truth” datasets

Telemanom (Detecting Spacecraft Anomalies Using LSTMs and Nonparametric Dynamic Thresholding; Hundman, Constantinou, Laporte, Colwell, Soderstrom; 2018 (NASA Jet Propulsion Laboratory) <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1802.04431.pdf>)

- Few dozens of time series, few thousands of values each, taken from SNAP and MSL NASA's missions
- Each series is split into training (no anomalies) and test parts (with anomalies)
 - Visual inspection shows that training part **may contain** anomalies
 - Data corrupted due to separate train/test normalization
 - Models trained on train parts generate values different that in the original paper
- No more public telemetry datasets

What about using OPS-SAT?

- OPS-SAT is a novel small satellite containing powerful on-board computer
- Available for execution of code and commands by external experimenters
- OPS-SAT's telemetry data is freely available to experimenters

OPS-SAT telemetry

- Few thousands of numeric telemetry series
 - Sampling rate 1s - 30s
- Commands sent from ground station

- Discontinuities in data
 - Poses problem while processing with Machine Learning models

Values of SEP8260p: continuous fragment above, gaps visible below

OPS-SAT, April 2021 – multivariate data example

```

period_s=5,begin=1617654990,length=3862,count=13.csv
1  TIMESTAMP_S,CADC0890,CADC0900,CADC0892,GS_T1347,CADC0884,GS_T1260,CADC0901,CADC0902,CADC0886,GS_T1259,CADC0888,GS_T1261,CADC0894
2  1617654990,0.0924375,0.0,0.0,1.36894,0.0,0.0,0.0,0.0,0.152267,0.0,0.0
3  1617654995,0.0970736,0.0,0.0,1.3431799999999998,0.0,0.0,0.0,0.0,0.152267,0.0,0.0
4  1617655000,0.0993924,0.0,0.0,1.36894,0.0,0.0,0.0,0.0,0.154868,0.0,0.0
5  1617655005,0.0993924,0.0,0.0,1.3431799999999998,0.0,0.0,0.0,0.0,0.160074,0.0,0.0
6  1617655010,0.104032,0.0,0.0,1.35568,0.0,0.0,0.0,0.0,0.162679,0.0,0.0
7  1617655015,0.106352,0.0,0.0,1.35568,0.0,0.0,0.0,0.0,0.167892,0.0,0.0
8  1617655020,0.110995,0.0,0.0,1.33132,0.0,0.0,0.0,0.0,0.1705,0.0,0.0
9  1617655025,0.113317,0.0,0.0,1.3431799999999998,0.0,0.0,0.0,0.0,0.175719,0.0,0.0
10 1617655030,0.117963,0.0,0.0,1.33132,0.0,0.0,0.0,0.0,0.175719,0.0,0.0
11 1617655035,0.117963,0.0,0.0,1.32002,0.0,0.0,0.0,0.0,0.183558,0.0,0.0
12 1617655040,0.12261199999999997,0.0,0.0,1.32002,0.0,0.0,0.0,0.0,0.183558,0.0,0.0
13 1617655045,0.136575,0.0,0.0,1.30919,0.0,0.0,0.0,0.0,0.18879,0.0,0.0
14 1617655050,0.131918,0.0,0.0,1.28874,0.0,0.0,0.0,0.0,0.18879,0.0,0.0
15 1617655055,0.141236,0.0,0.0,1.2987799999999998,0.0,0.0,0.0,0.0,0.194028,0.0,0.0
16 1617655060,0.136575,0.0,0.0,1.27905,0.0,0.0,0.0,0.0,0.194028,0.0,0.0
17 1617655065,0.150565,0.0,0.0,1.26965,0.0,0.0,0.0,0.0,0.196648,0.0,0.0
18 1617655070,0.159908,0.0,0.0,1.26965,0.0,0.0,0.0,0.0,0.186174,0.0,0.0
19 1617655075,0.1529,0.0,0.0,1.26053,0.0,0.0,0.0,0.0,0.08752,0.0,0.0
20 1617655080,0.173949,0.0,0.0,1.23461,0.0,0.0,0.0,0.0,0.0154256,0.0,0.0
21 1617655085,0.183329,0.0,0.0,1.23461,0.603286,0.0,0.0,-0.76455,0.0102835,-0.226959,0.0
22 1617655090,0.195077,0.0,0.0,1.24303,0.0,0.0,0.0,0.0,0.0359994,0.0,0.0
23 1617655095,0.202139,0.0,0.0,1.21835,0.0,0.0,0.0,0.0,0.126306,0.0,0.0
24 1617655100,0.216294,0.0,0.0,1.21835,0.0,0.0,0.0,0.0,0.141871,0.0,0.0
25 1617655105,0.230493,0.0,0.0,1.20278,0.0,0.0,0.0,0.0,0.13408499999999998,0.0,0.0
26 1617655110,0.242361,0.0,0.0,1.20278,0.0,0.0,0.0,0.0,0.123715,0.0,0.0
27 1617655115,0.261424,0.0,0.0,1.18054,0.0,0.0,0.0,0.0,0.110772,0.0,0.0
28 1617655120,0.270992,0.0,0.0,1.18054,0.0,0.0,0.0,0.0,0.0926826,0.0,0.0
29 1617655125,0.290205,0.0,0.0,0.00268713,1.15944,0.0,0.0,0.0,0.07720160000000001,0.0,0.0
30 1617655130,0.304687,0.0,0.0,0.00268713,1.15944,0.0,0.0,0.0,0.0617392,0.0,0.0
31 1617655135,0.31437800000000005,0.0,0.0,0.0564597,1.13931,0.0,0.0,0.0,0.0488653,0.0,0.0
32 1617655140,0.3241,0.0,0.0,0.0645358,1.13931,0.0,0.0,0.0,0.0,0.0,0.0
33 1617655145,0.244739,0.0,0.0,0.0699223,1.11377,0.0,0.0,0.0,0.0,0.0,0.0
34 1617655150,0.331412,0.0,0.0,1.12003,0.0,0.0,0.0,0.0,0.0,0.0,0.0
35 1617655155,0.336297,0.0,0.0,1.131,1.09545,0.0,0.0,0.0,0.0,0.0,0.0
36 1617655160,0.338742,0.0,0.0,1.09545,0.0,0.0,0.0,0.0,0.0,0.0,0.0
37 1617655165,0.336297,0.0,0.0,1.0701079999999998,1.0836,0.0,0.0,0.0,0.0,0.0,0.0
38 1617655170,0.346092,0.0,0.0,1.089226,1.07777,0.0,0.0,0.0,0.0,0.0,0.0
39 1617655175,0.331412,0.0,0.0,1.072,0.0,0.0,0.0,0.0,0.0,0.0,0.0
40 1617655180,0.0,0.0,0.0,0.0,0.0,0.0,0.0,0.0,0.0,0.0,0.0

```

period_s=5,begin=1617654990,length=3862,count=13.csv

Anomalies (?) in GST1222

real vs. predictions on the training sequence

test sequence and potential anomalies:

- red – "GT" marked by visual inspection,
- blue & purple – ranges found by our method

Anomalies (?) in CADC0973

real vs. predictions on training sequence

test sequence and potential anomalies:

- red – "GT" marked by visual inspection,
- blue & purple – ranges found by our method

Towards digital twins and simulations...

Towards digital twins and simulations...

Towards digital twins and simulations...

Antelope Toolbox

Detection

Simulation

Setup

Simulation
Enabled:

Clear graph

Refresh
speed [s]:

0.2s

Example

P-3

Anomaly

Create anomaly

Anomaly
time [s]:

4.1s

Anomaly type:

random

Min value

-1

Max value

1

Detector

RNN Based

Detector model:

Example

P-3

Selected detector model: P-3 (25 input(s))

Measuring the quality of anomaly detection

- Example quality metrics:
 - NAB Score (Numenta Anomaly Benchmark)
 - Dice coefficient: $2 \times |X \cap Y| / (|X| + |Y|)$
 - F-score and other metrics based on the confusion matrix

Measuring the quality of anomaly detection

- Example quality metrics:
 - NAB Score (Numenta Anomaly Benchmark)
 - Dice coefficient: $2 \times |X \cap Y| / (|X| + |Y|)$
 - F-score and other metrics based on the confusion matrix
- **Various metrics are used across papers**
- All metrics are designed for **supervised set-ups**

Conclusions

- The community **lacks good anomaly detection datasets**
- **Digital twins and simulations** may help us these issues
- **Our anomaly detection looks promising** in finding potential anomalies (TBV, e.g., in OPS-SAT)
 - The entire process runs in **unsupervised mode**
- **Determining metrics to quantify the anomaly detection** is a (huge) challenge → we need rigorous quantitative, qualitative and statistical validation

Antelope: Towards on-board anomaly detection in telemetry data using deep learning

Jakub Nalepa, Michal Myller, Pawel Benecki, Jacek Andrzejewski, and Daniel Kostrzewa

jnalepa@kplabs.pl

KP Labs Sp. z o.o,
ul. Stanisława Konarskiego 18C,
44-100 Gliwice,

info@kplabs.pl

www.kplabs.pl